

Validation of Physics-based and Data-driven Models using Measured SAFARI-1 Axial Neutron Flux Profiles

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a comprehensive validation of SAFARI-1 research reactor full 3D MCNP model and a 3D convolutional neural network (CNN) surrogate model for predicting the reactor's axial neutron flux profiles. Both models are benchmarked against experimental measurements and against each other, providing a robust assessment of their predictive capabilities. Uncertainty quantification is incorporated for the CNN surrogate, enabling confidence estimation in its predictions. The MCNP model is extended to additional operational cycles to assess its generalization capability. Results show that the CNN model predictions closely match both the MCNP simulations and the experimental measurements, while offering a significant computational speedup. This work demonstrates the potential of combining physics-based and data-driven approaches for efficient reactor monitoring and safety analysis, and contributes to machine learning verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification in nuclear applications.

Keywords: Physics-based, data-driven, neutron flux profiles, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have been extensively applied in the nuclear industry to accurately predict key reactor physics parameters. Examples include the use of Radial Basis Function and Multi-Layer Perceptron models to predict power peaking factors [1]; Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) to estimate assembly axial neutron flux profiles [2, 3], control rod positions, and cycle lengths [4]; and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for diagnosing abnormalities in nuclear power plants [5], prediction of assembly and pin-level parameters such as pin-powers and multiplication factor [6], and optimizing in-core fuel management [7]. These ML models, trained on either computational or experimental data, provide accurate approximations with several orders of magnitude of speedup when compared to conventional simulation methods. Simulation codes are generally used to calculate reactor operational parameters and have been validated using experimental data. However, both simulations and measurements are subject to limitations, approximations, and uncertainties. In such cases, surrogate models trained on historical measurement data can provide additional insight on the predicted quantity of interest, and thus complement both experiments and neutronic code simulations.

In the SAFARI-1 research reactor, a 20 MWth tank-in-pool material testing reactor, in-core axial neutron flux measurements are performed at the beginning of each cycle using copper wires inserted along the active core height [8]. These data are used to estimate safety-related parameters and validate neutronic codes, but are often affected by measurement noise, missing data, or shifted flux profiles due to experimental limitations. Previous studies [2, 3, 9] applied DNNs, Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs), Deep Ensembles (DE) and Gaussian Processes (GPs) to improve the prediction of the flux profile and subsequently correct the deficiencies, achieving good agreement with the experimental data.

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CNNs have been widely and successfully applied in image recognition, making them well-suited for analyzing reactor cores, where the fuel assembly configuration resembles a two-dimensional grid-like structure. Leveraging this similarity, CNNs can effectively model and evaluate core parameters such as axial neutron flux profiles and fuel-loading patterns. Based on these advantages, this study introduces a method for enhancing SAFARI-1 reactor operational support by evaluating CNN models against traditional high-fidelity Monte Carlo N-Particle (MCNP) [10] simulations. Specifically, a CNN framework is developed for predicting axial neutron flux profiles, with comparisons established between CNN predictions, MCNP simulations, and copper-wires experimental measurements to support validation of both the CNN and MCNP models. This paper presents a comprehensive validation of both a full 3D MCNP model and a 3D CNN surrogate for the SAFARI-1 reactor, using real measurement data as the reference and cross-comparing the models to each other. The surrogate model is further enhanced with uncertainty quantification (UQ), supporting robust and trustworthy predictions.

2. METHODOLOGIES

2.1. Training Dataset

Copper wire activation is a long-established technique used to measure the neutron flux distribution in SAFARI-1. Aluminium blades containing copper wires are inserted along the active height of 26 fuel assemblies and six fuel follower assemblies (one regulating- and five control rods) and irradiated at ~ 500 kW for 15–20 minutes. The β -decay of ^{64}Cu (half-life: 12.7 h) is then measured to obtain axial thermal neutron flux profiles at 180 equidistant points along each wire for all 32 assemblies. These data were used to train ML models in previous studies [2, 3, 9]. In these studies, 180 axial positions and six control bank position (one regulating rod plus five control rods treated as a single bank) were employed as model inputs, with detector counts representing the output flux profiles. In this study, the regulating rod position is treated separately and incorporated as an additional input feature, alongside control bank positions and axial locations. The dataset comprises 13 cycles, providing up to 74 880 data points for training. Preprocessing included reconstruction of missing points via interpolation or extrapolation to standardize all profiles to 180 axial points, followed by input-output z-score standardization.

2.2. MCNP Model

The as-built SAFARI-1 full-core MCNP model, derived from the OSCAR-5 [11] heterogeneous 3D model is shown in Figure 1. The model uses the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data libraries and simulation are done with MCNP 6.3. The cycle C1109-1 (i.e., September 2011) was used to simulate copper-wire activation experiment as described before. To improve computational efficiency and tally convergence, each 1 mm copper wire was represented by a larger diluted copper region of equivalent mass and subdivided into 16 axial segments to capture axial flux variations. The main activation reactions, $^{63}\text{Cu}(n, \gamma)^{64}\text{Cu}$ and $^{65}\text{Cu}(n, \gamma)^{66}\text{Cu}$, were tallied using the FM4 card. Criticality simulations were performed in KCODE mode with 100 inactive and 3 000 active cycles of 100 000 neutrons per cycle, yielding $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.00089$ ($\simeq 89$ pcm) and reaction-rate uncertainties $<5\%$ at thermal energies (<0.625 eV). The particle histories were chosen to balance computational cost and were not fully optimized for minimum uncertainty. Resulting reaction rates were compared with measured data and CNN predictions for validation.

2.3. 3D CNN Surrogate Model and UQ

2.3.1. Design and Training

The CNN was developed using three input features: (1) the five control bank position, (2) the regulating rod position, and (3) the axial locations. The output predicts assembly-specific detector counts or flux profiles. The model was built on the SAFARI-1 (9×8) core layout (Figure. 1), which includes 26 fuel and

Figure 1. The SAFARI-1 reactor (a) radial core configuration and (b) full core MCNP model.

six follower-type control assemblies. For simplicity, non-essential reflector and structural positions were removed, yielding a (7×7) grid containing all 32 relevant assemblies. The control bank and regulating rod positions, as well as the axial locations were mapped onto this (7×7) grid, forming an input tensor of size $(7 \times 7 \times 180 \times 3)$, with detector counts at 180 axial points as output. Note that the control bank position data was only mapped onto the six control rod positions, with the remaining positions filled with zeros and handled using Keras Masking so that missing data were ignored during training. The final architecture (Table I) consists of an input and masking layer, three convolution-pooling blocks, and two fully connected layers, using ReLU activations. The optimized hyperparameters, obtained using random search and grid search, include a learning rate of 2.35×10^{-4} , L1/L2 regularization of $1.39 \times 10^{-6}/3.58 \times 10^{-4}$, a dropout rate of 0.02, and a batch size of 32. After preprocessing, 13 cycles were available: 11 for training/validation/testing and 2 for prediction. This produced 1980 samples per assembly (63360 for 32 assemblies). Data were randomly split into 85% for training and 15% for testing/validation. Model performance was assessed using mean absolute error (MAE).

Table I. Architecture of the 3D CNN showing topology and modifiable parameters

Layer name	Type	Output dimensions	No. parameters
input 1	InputLayer	(7, 7, 180, 3)	0
masking	Masking	(7, 7, 180, 3)	0
conv3d one	Conv3D	(7, 7, 180, 35)	2870
max pooling3d	MaxPooling3D	(4, 4, 90, 35)	0
conv3d two	Conv3D	(4, 4, 90, 75)	70950
max pooling3d 1	MaxPooling3D	(2, 2, 45, 75)	0
conv3d three	Conv3D	(2, 2, 45, 354)	717204
max pooling3d 2	MaxPooling3D	(1, 1, 23, 354)	0
flatten	Flatten	(8142)	0
dense one	Dense	(840)	6840120
dropout	Dropout	(840)	0
dense two	Dense	(5760)	4844160
reshape	Reshape	(32, 180)	0
Trainable parameters			12475304

2.3.2. Deep Ensemble for UQ

Deep ensemble (DE) serves as a UQ method for neural network models by training M models to predict a distribution of parameters and aggregating their predictions [12]. In the case of this study, the output distribution is assumed to be Gaussian, whose mean and variance parameters are directly predicted by the CNN model. To perform this, a negative log-likelihood (NLL) loss function is used instead of the standard mean absolute error loss, initially used when training the CNN:

$$\mathcal{L}_\theta(x_i, y_i) = -\log p_\theta(y_i|x_i) = \frac{\log \sigma_\theta(x_i)}{2} + \frac{(y_i - \mu_\theta(x_i))^2}{2\sigma_\theta^2(x_i)} + \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

where $\{x_i, y_i\}$ represents the input and output in the i^{th} training data sample. The uncertainty across the predictions for each axial flux profile is assumed to be heteroscedastic in nature. To allow the variance to vary across instances, the model is tasked with generating predictions which are averaged across all models ($\mu_\theta(x_i)$) and the variance of each prediction $\sigma_\theta^2(x_i)$. The mean of the variance predictions are taken to derive the aleatoric uncertainty ($\mathbb{E}_\theta[\sigma_\theta^2(x_i)]$), while the variance of flux profile predictions produced the epistemic uncertainty ($\text{Var}_\theta[\mu_\theta(x_i)]$). The summation of these two uncertainties is used to obtain the total uncertainty. Five CNNs are used to perform DE UQ as instructed by [12].

2.3.3. Conformal Prediction for UQ

Recently, conformal prediction (CP) has emerged as a statistically rigorous method for quantifying predictive uncertainty with guaranteed coverage given certain conditions [13]. CP provides the formal guarantee that within the probability of a desired confidence interval ($1 - \alpha$) the prediction interval produced by CP ($\mathcal{C}(X_{\text{test}})$) contains the target value (Y_{test}) as expressed in Equation (2).

$$\mathbb{P}(Y_{\text{test}} \in \mathcal{C}(X_{\text{test}})) \geq 1 - \alpha \quad (2)$$

This formal guarantee holds, regardless of data distribution or model used, by assuming all samples are independent and identically distributed or exchangeable. Traditional CP provides uniform prediction intervals, which are uninformative for heteroscedastic variances. To provide instance-wise uncertainty, a difficulty estimator (Diff-E) may be used. The Diff-E allows for locally adaptive uncertainty intervals for datapoints that are not or rarely present in the calibration dataset. This interval adjustment is based on the k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) Euclidean distance of predicted datapoints to those in the calibration dataset. 5% of the total dataset was randomly chosen to construct the calibration dataset. A prediction interval using a kNN-based Diff-E was implemented using the CREPES Python module [14] using a confidence interval of 95% and 25 neighbors for the kNN algorithm.

2.3.4. Bayesian CNN for UQ

The final UQ method utilized is a Bayesian CNN (B-CNN), which trains the CNN to learn a distribution over its parameters (trainable weights and biases) rather than learning deterministic values. The network is created to learn a probability distribution of the model's parameters, θ , after being trained on the data, \mathcal{D} , using Bayes' theorem $p(\theta|\mathcal{D}) = p(\mathcal{D}|\theta)p(\theta)/p(\mathcal{D})$.

Generating an exact solution for the posterior, $p(\theta|\mathcal{D})$, in a CNN with millions of parameters is mathematically intractable; therefore, *Bayes by Backprop* is used [15]. A variational approximation of the posterior distribution, q , is defined such that: $q_\theta(\mathbf{w}|\mathcal{D}) \approx p(\theta|\mathcal{D})$ where \mathbf{w} represents a set of the network's weight distributions such that each weight, $w_i \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$. As both μ and σ^2 are learned, the amount of trainable parameters in the CNN model essentially doubles, leading to noisy gradients and exploding losses. To maintain model stability during training, the Bayesian CNN is created, where the final output layer is Bayesian while the remaining layers remain deterministic. Similarly to the DE method, a heteroscedastic uncertainty is assumed. Therefore, the B-CNN is created to output both its nominal prediction and the variance, which is trained using the NLL loss function in Equation (1).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section compares data-driven CNN predictions and MCNP simulations against each other and against measurements for validation. UQ of CNN model is performed using DE, CP, and BNN methods. The analysis is based on cycle C1109-1, and only selected assemblies are shown due to the large volume of the results. The analysis presented for the UQ results is taken from a separate cycle, C2403-1 (taken in March 2024).

3.1. MCNP and CNN Results Comparison

The 3D CNN and MCNP results were compared with experimental data for assemblies C6 (fuel) and G5 (followers) in cycle C1109-1. For consistency, both the MCNP reaction rates and ML-predicted counts were normalized to their axial averages (Figure 2). The MCNP error bars indicate relative uncertainties below 8%, demonstrating good precision. As shown in Figure 2, both MCNP and the ML models reproduce the measured axial trends, with some discrepancies in the follower assemblies. The ML predictions are smooth, capturing the overall trend without being affected by measurement noise. MCNP also follows the general trend but includes visible uncertainty.

Figure 2. CNN predictions compared to MCNP reaction rates (RR) for C6 and G5 axial flux profiles.

The top and bottom flux dips in the aluminum structures are generally well reproduced, except where profiles are axially shifted—observable from the positions of the thermal peaks—and in the coupling piece at the top of the follower assemblies. This is most evident in G5, where MCNP deviates from both the measurements and CNN results. This behavior is expected: the CNN model learns both the underlying trends and some measurement noise, while MCNP provides a noise-free physical prediction. The contrast between measurement noise, CNN, and MCNP’s systematic modeling underlines the importance of data quality and careful training strategies for robust predictive performance.

The heatmaps in Figure 3 compare axially-averaged counts for cycle C1109-1 across assemblies, with the third value indicating the relative error (%) between the comparisons for each plot. The CNN closely reproduces MCNP trends and matches the measured data well, effectively capturing the spatial distribution, including the lower-count peripheral regions. MCNP shows the largest deviations in the control assemblies, whereas the CNN performs better in these areas due to being trained on measured data. These results demonstrate the strong potential of the 3D CNN model to enhance predictive capability for SAFARI-1 neutron flux profiles and support the development of real-time monitoring tools, while also providing a useful validation framework for both MCNP and CNN models.

(a) Measured (First) vs CNN (Second)

(b) Measured (First) vs MCNP (Second)

(c) MCNP (First) vs CNN (Second)

Figure 3. Axially averaged count distribution for cycle C1109-1 with percentage relative error (third value).

3.2. UQ of CNN Predictions

The accuracies for both the base CNN (used when performing DE and CP) and Bayesian CNN are measured through the R^2 score, mean absolute error (MAE), and Mean Absolute Percent Error (MAPE) and presented in Table II. Both models are found to perform similarly, with the Bayesian CNN producing larger residuals, likely because twice as many parameters are optimized in the output layer. The relative uncertainties, expressed as a percentage, found from DE, CP, and the Bayesian CNN are found to be 10.48%, 11.75%, and 16.16%, respectively.

The 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for each of the UQ methods are illustrated in Figure 4. Similar to the presented relative uncertainties, the 95% CI for the Bayesian CNN is found to be the largest. The shape of the CI produced by CP is found to be irregular compared to those produced by DE and Bayesian CNN. This irregularity is a consequence of the kNN difficulty estimator as predicted data points with a larger Euclidean distance from data points in the calibration set are found by the kNN model to be

Table II. Comparison of baseline CNN to Bayesian CNN accuracies

Model	R^2	MAE (Counts)	MAPE (%)
Base CNN	0.980	24.945	8.644
Bayesian CNN	0.975	28.935	10.481

more difficult to predict. This larger estimation of difficulty results in a more conservative CI for that instance in the prediction set.

It is observed that the first five measured data points for the C6 assembly largely drift from the overall pattern of the data, leading to large local errors in the CNN prediction for these data points. These irregular data points may be attributed to experimental error and are considered as outliers. When predicting these data points, the 95% CI for the Bayesian CNN is found to increase in the direction of the outliers largely. At the beginning of the dataset, both CP and DE exhibit a similar behavior to a lesser magnitude. Overall, the Bayesian CNN is found to be the most conservative in performing UQ.

Figure 4. Comparison of UQ results from Bayesian CNN, DE and CP for C2403-1.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a comprehensive validation of both a full 3D MCNP model and a 3D CNN surrogate for the SAFARI-1 reactor, using real measurement data as the reference and cross-comparing the models to each other. The surrogate model is further enhanced with UQ, supporting robust and trustworthy predictions. Both the MCNP and CNN models were demonstrated to provide relatively accurate prediction of the axial neutron flux profiles when compared to measurement data. UQ was performed using DE, CP, and Bayesian CNN. The Bayesian CNN is found to be the most conservative when estimating model uncertainty.

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